

HEALTH LOCUS OF CONTROL AND GENDER FACTORS IN HEALTH RECOVERY OF HOSPITALIZED PATIENTS

Dagona, Zubairu Kwambo, Haruna Karick and Nimchak Melissa Julya
Department of Psychology, University of Jos, Jos, Nigeria

ABSTRACT

215 patients comprising 103 males and 112 females were studied two instrument, the multidimensional health locus of control scale (MHLC)(Ensfield,1998) which measures health locus of control (Externality – Internality) and the personal vision of recovery questionnaire (PVRQ)(Wallston, Wallston, & Devilish, 1978) that measures health recovery. Data were subjected to 2×2 ANOVA. Result indicated that; health locus of control had significant effect on health recovery $F(1,211) = 669.399, P < 0.05$. Likewise gender main effect had a significant effect on health recovery $F(1,211) = 34.692 P < 0.05$. The interaction effects of health locus of control and gender on health recovery was also significant $F(2441, 211) = 11.107$ the implication of the findings dwell on training of patients to change their locus of control which aids in recovery.

KEYWORDS: multidimensional health, health recovery, attitudes and beliefs, Jos

Received for Publication: 28/08/13

Accepted for Publication: 20/11/13

Corresponding Author: harunakarick@yahoo.com

INTRODUCTION

Affirmative attitudes and beliefs about health and self may increase the likelihood that people will behave wisely in high risk situation and may strive under adverse conditions such as poverty, bereavement and other stressful life events. It is based on this understanding that Rotter developed the locus of control theory. Rotter (1975), cautioned that internality and externality represent two ends of a continuum, not an either or typology. Internals tend to attribute outcomes of events to their own control.

Externals attribute outcomes of events to external circumstances. Due to their locating control outside themselves, externals tend to feel they have less control over their fate; people with external locus of control tend to be more stressed and prone to clinical depression, (Maltby, Day & Mackill, 2007). Internals were believed by Rotter (1966) to exhibit essential characteristics, high achievement motivation and low outer directedness. This was the basics of locus of control scale proposed by Rotter. He believed that locus of control is one dimensional construct.

Locus of control's most famous application has probably been in the area of health psychology, largely the work of Kenneth Wallston. Measures of locus of control in the health domains were reviewed by Furnhani & steel(1993), the most famous of this would be the health locus of control scale and the multidimensional health locus of control scale, or MHLC (Wallston & Devellis, 1976; Wallston, Kaplan & Maides, 1976). The Rotter scale is based on the idea, echoing levenson's earlier work that health may be attributed to three possible outcomes, internal factors such as ones self determination of a healthy life style powerful other such as one's doctor, or luck. These authors noted that certain health related behaviors are related to internal health locus of control. Overall studies using behavior specific health of control scales tended to produce more positive results (Lefcourt, 1991, Gwandure, 2010). Moreover these measures have been found to be more predictive of general behavior than more general measures, such as the MHLC scale (Norman & Bennett, 1995). These authors cited several studies that used health related locus of control scales in specific domains including smoking cessation (Georgio and Bradley, 1992), diabetes (Fmaro, price, Desmond, & Roberts, 1987) tablet treated diabetes (Bradley, Levis, Jennings & Ward, 1990), hypertension (Stantion, 1987) arthritis (Nicasio et al, 1985), cancer (Pruyn, et al 1988) and heart and lung disease (Allison, 1987). They also argued that health locus of control is

Journals© 2013. All rights reserved

This work by [Wilolud Journals](http://www.wiloludjournal.com) is licensed under a [Creative Commons Attribution 3.0 Unported License](http://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/3.0/)

better at predicting health related behavior if studied in conjunction with health value i.e. the value attached to their health, suggesting that health locus of control is important moderator variable in the health locus of control relationship. For instance Weiss & Harson (1990), cited in Norman and Bennett, 1995) found increased relationship between internal health locus of control and health when health value was assessed.

Health locus of control was also subjected to studies on gender differences and adjustment to persistent pain. Kingston & Smith (1997), studied 160 patients (67males and 93 females) referred to a comprehensive pain rehabilitation program. Three unique MHLC profile clusters were identified for both males and females. Among men, cluster assignment was related to age only. The younger male participants reported a strong internal attribution style. Older male patients relied more heavily on both chance and powerful other factors. Among women cluster assignment was related to the use of coping strategies.

Globally studies on HLOC are scarce, further studies showing gender differences are not conclusive especially in African population. It is with this background that the present study seeks to address the following hypotheses.

- (a). Gender would have a statistically significant effect on health recovery of patients.
- (b). Health locus of control would have a statistically significant effect on health recovery of patients.
- (c). Health locus of control and gender would interact to have a statistically significant effect on health recovery of patients.

METHOD

Participants: Two hundred and fifteen (215) patients comprising of one hundred and three males (103) and one hundred and twelve females (112) in a teaching hospital were studied. Their ages ranged from fifteen (15) to forty six (46) years. The patients were drawn from MOPD (medical outpatient department), GOPD (general outpatient department), APIN (AIDS prevention Initiative in Nigeria), Physiotherapy and ophthalmology wards and clinics as well as hospitalized patients (inpatients). Most patients have more than primary level of education.

Design: the study is 2x2 factorial design, where the independent variable (IDV) locus of control has two levels (Internal and external) independent (IDV) variable of gender (male and female) and a dependent variable (DV) health recovery.

Ethical consideration:

Informed consent: the authority of the teaching hospital perused and discussed the submission by the researchers to get the permission to conduct the study. Issues discussed included reasons for carrying out the research; what the participation would entail; potential harm/safety of the participants; benefits of the research; confidentiality of responses and consent of the participants who were adults. At the end of discussion the authority granted a written ethical clearance to undertake the study.

Instruments: Two instruments were used for the study these included the multidimensional health locus of control (MHLC) and personal vision of recovery questionnaire (PVRQ). The MHLC was developed by Wallston, Wallston & Devellis (1978), it composed of 18 items with three subscales (a) Internal health locus of control (IHLC) contains 1,6,8,12,13 and 17 (sample item, `I get sick, it is my own behavior which determines how soon I get well again`) (b) Powerful health locus of control (PHLC) contains 2,4,9,11,15 and 16 (sample item, `whenever I do not feel well, I should consult a medical professional`), (c) Chance health locus of control (CHLC) contains items 3,5,7,10,14 and 18 (sample item: `my good health is largely a matter of good fortune`) these items were rated using six point Likert scale ranging from `1` strongly disagree to `6` strongly agree. Score for each subscale can range from 6 – 36. Index of internal consistency for the three subscales is between 0.65 and 0.75 and, test retest reliability is between 0.70 and 0.80. Reliability coefficient for the study were 0.70 (IHLC) 0.68 (PHLC) and 0.48 (CHLC) The personal vision of recovery questionnaire (PVRQ: Ensfield, Steffen, Borkin, & Schafer, 1998) was designed to measure consumers` beliefs about own recovery. Developed by a team of professional and consumer researchers through a participatory process, the scale was created to capture the consumer perspective of the highly personal multifaceted process (Ensfield,1998) responses to the PVRQ are coded on a scale of `5` to `1` (strongly agree to strongly disagree). Items are summed across each subscale and weigh equally. Items such as `spirituality is a part of my recovery`, etc. are reflected.

Procedure:

Hospital patients were approached by the researchers, both inpatient and out patients were used. On approach a letter of introduction from the researchers department was given to the patient after the usual cultural greetings to the patient and asking after his/her condition and a prayer for a quick recovery. The researchers also presented to the participant an identity card. If the patient was convinced into participation then the instructions would be read out to her/him and the consent form from the hospital and the questionnaires were administered. Every participant was given a pen to circle the responses that matched his/her opinion. If any item needed clarification the researcher helped in doing that. At the end of eight weeks two hundred and eighty questionnaires were administered and two hundred and fifteen (215) met the criteria. Sixty-five of the questionnaires were invalidated, because some participants circled some responses twice or more and some were unable to complete all the information.

The completed questionnaires were coded and subjected to SPSS statistical packages analysis.

RESULTS

Results obtained from the analysis are presented below

Table1: DESCRIPTIVE STATISTICS OF DEPENDENT VARIABLE: PERSONAL VISION OF RECOVERY

Gender of Participants	Health locos of control	Mean	Std. deviation	N
Male	Internal	97.12	4.616	69
	External	80.88	3.914	34
	Total	91.76	8.832	103
Female	Internal	95.27	5.369	62
	External	74.24	5.988	50
	Total	85.88	11.196	112
Total	Internal	96.24	5.052	131
	External	76.93	6.166	84
	Total	88.70	10.931	215

The results of Table1 show that male internal patients have higher mean scores on health recovery (97.12) than female internal mean score (95.27), suggesting a better health recovery by male gender than female.

Table 2: ANOVA SOURCE TABLE OF HEALTH LOCUS OF CONTROL AND GENDER ON HEALTH

Dependent variable: PERSONAL VISION OF RECOVERY					
Source	Type III sum of square	df	Mean square	F	Sig.
Corrected Model	20099.288a	3	6699.763	258.434	.000
Intercept	1508928.803	1	1508928.803	58204.836	.000
Gender	899.373	1	899.373	34.692	.000
HLC	17353.817	1	17353.817	699.399	.000
Gender * HLC	287.952	1	287.952	11.107	.001
Error	54700.061	211	25.924		
Total	1717034.000	215			
Corrected Total	25569.329	214			

a. R squared = .786 (Adjusted R squared = .783)

The ANOVA results in Table 2 show that there is a statistically significant differences between genders on their health recovery, with males rating higher than females $F(1, 211) = 34.692, p < 0.05$. Likewise health locus of control has a statistically significant effect on health recovery of patients. Patients with internal health locus of control have been found to rate higher on health recovery than patients with external health locus of control orientation $F(1, 211) = 669.399, p < 0.05$. Further analysis from table two also shows that the interaction effect of gender and health locus of control is statistically significant. Indicating that males with higher rating on health locus of control orientation scored higher on health recovery than female patients, $F(1, 211) = 11.107, p < 0.05$

DISCUSSION

This study explored the different types of health locus of control and the role each played in accuracy of perception of patients on health recovery and health behaviors of individuals. Hypothesis that gender would have a statistical significant effect on health recovery was confirmed. The result was consistent with previous research (Mamlin, Harris & Case, 2001) their research has found the following result (a) Males tend to be more internal than females (b) as people get older they tend to be more internal. In our culture men tend to be placed in responsibilities which exercise the sense of personal control. They try to be more achievement oriented and get better paid jobs which give them additional sense of control which has been the major characteristic of internals; in most cultures the men control the other gender.

Roberts *et al.* (2002) explained the sex differences with men perceiving greater influence of powerful others and chance factors in their acute back pain than women participants.

The hypothesis on HLC would affect health recovery was also significant and in support of early research findings on locus of control and health (Rotter 1966; Skinner, 1971). Other researchers have found significant differences on health recovery associated with self-control among patients. Participants with an external locus of control perceived themselves as not capable of effectively reducing health risk associated with self-control (Mullins & Rothe 2008). This means that external people not only believe that events are beyond their control, but they do so either in terms of chance or powerful others. Internal locus of control individuals are more likely to be achievement oriented because they see that their own behaviors result in positive effects; and they are more likely to be achievers as well. External locus of control individuals tend to be less independent and also are more likely to be depressed and stressed thus worsening their conditions. Hence indicating that health locus of control has an effect on health recovery of patients.

REFERENCES

- Ensfield, L.B. (1998). The personal vision of recovery questionnaire. The development of a consumer derived scale. Unpublished doctoral dissertation, University of Cincinnati. Cincinnati, OH.
- Furnhani, A. & Steele, H. (1993). Measures of locus of control: A critique of children's health and work related locus of control questionnaires. *British Journal of Psychology* 84.443-79.
- Gwandure, C. (2010). The development, implementation and evaluation of a locus of control based training programme for HIV/AIDS risk reduction among university students. Unpublished PhD thesis, Nelson Mandela University, Cape Town, South Africa.
- Kingston, R.S. & Smith J.P (1997) Socioeconomic status and racial and ethnic differences in functional status associated with chronic diseases. *American Journal of Public Health*, 87(5), p805-810
- Lefcourt, H.M & Davidson-Katz, K. (1991). Locus of control and health. In Snyder, C.R & Forsyth, D.R (eds). Handbook of social and clinical psychology: *The Health Perspective*, p 246 -266
- Maltby J., Day, L., & Macaskill, A. (2007). Personality, individual differences and intelligence. Harlow: Pearson Prentice Hall.

Mamlin, N., Harris, K.R & Case, L.P.(2001)A methodological analyses of research on locus of control and learning disabilities: Rethinking a common assumption. *Journal of Special Education*. Winter.

Mullins, C.W., & Rothe, D.L.(2008).Gold, diamonds and blood: international state corporate crime in the democratic republic of Congo. *Contemporary Justice Review: Issues in Criminal, Social and Restorative Justice*,11, p81-99.

Norman S., & Bennet, P. (1995). Health locus of control. In Conner, M. & Norman, P. Predicting health behaviour. Buckingham: Open University Press. P 62- 94

Roberts *et al.* (2002). Perception of health locus of control in people with acute lower back pain. *Physiotherapy*, 88(9) p 543- 548

Rotter, J.B. (1954). Social learning and clinical psychology. NY: Prentice- Hall.

Rotter, J.B. (1975).Some problems and misconceptions related to the construct of internal versus external control if reinforcement. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology* 43: 56-67.

Rotter, J.B. (1966).Generalized expectancies for internal versus external locus of control of reinforcement. *Psychological Monographs*.33(1),300-303.

Wallston, K. A., Kaplan O. D., & Maides, S.A. (1976). Development and validation of health locus of control (HLC) scale. *Journal of Consulting and Clinical Psychology*, 44,p 580-585.

Wallston, K.A., Wallston, B.S., & Devellis, R. (1978). Development of multidimensional health locus of control(MHLC) scales. *Health Education Monograph* 6(2).160-170.
